

Practical Transmitters for MC: Functionalized Nanodevices Employing Cooperative Transmembrane Transport Proteins

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Abstract—This paper presents a novel optically controllable molecular communication (MC) transmitter (TX) design based on vesicular nanodevices (NDs), functionalized for controlled signaling molecule release via transmembrane proteins. All system components are chemically realizable, bridging the gap between MC theory and practical implementation. The NDs enable optical-to-chemical signal conversion, making them suitable as externally controllable TXs in various MC systems. The proposed design comprises two cooperating modules, namely an energizing and a release module, allowing the release of different signaling molecules depending on the module configuration. We introduce a general system model and provide a detailed mathematical analysis of a specific TX realization, deriving both exact and approximate analytical expressions for the released signaling molecule concentration, which are validated via numerical methods. The proposed model also accounts for the impact of buffering media commonly present in experimental or in-body environments. We further incorporate the impact of multiple NDs and parameter randomness inherent to vesicle synthesis into our model. The proposed models for single and multiple ND scenarios enable system parameter optimization, aiding the future experimental realization of the proposed MC TXs.

Index Terms—Molecular communication (MC), nanobiotechnology, synthetic biology, mathematical models.

I. INTRODUCTION

MOLECULAR communication (MC) is a burgeoning research area in the field of communication engineering and focuses on the development of communication systems that use signaling molecules (SMs) as information carriers

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[2], [3]. Diverging from conventional electromagnetic (EM) wave-based communication, MC has emerged as a novel paradigm, with the potential to facilitate communication in scenarios where EM wave-based methods face limitations, such as in liquid environments or at nanoscale. Therefore, MC offers numerous revolutionary prospective applications including health monitoring, targeted drug delivery (TDD), or the detection of toxic agents [2], [4], [5]. The successful deployment of MC systems largely depends on the development of *practically realizable* and *controllable* transmitter (TX) designs¹ that ideally support various types of SMs and are applicable in different environments (e.g., flow- and diffusion-dominated) to enlarge the range of future applications. However, the majority of research on TXs in MC is theoretical and often relies on unrealistic assumptions such as perfect controllability of the TX release dynamics or instantaneous release of SMs [6], [7]. Recently, more realistic TX models have been considered. In [8], a molecule harvesting TX, which is capable of (re-)uptake and release of SMs, was proposed. In [9], the controlled release of SMs by pH-driven membrane permeability switches was considered. The authors of [10] introduced a modified cell-based membrane fusion TX design, which allows for the release of SMs by the fusion of SM-carrying vesicles and the membrane of the TX. Additionally, a microscale flow-based TX design based on chemical reactions taking place in a microfluidic chip was introduced in [11]. Similarly, in [12], a microfluidic TX utilizing hydrodynamic gating was proposed. Nevertheless, there is a lack of externally controllable nanoscale TX designs that can also operate in absence of flow and microfluidic infrastructure. However, such a design is crucial for applications such as nanobioreactors. For such scenarios, vesicle-based TX designs leveraging transmembrane transport proteins are suitable. Initial studies for such designs have been conducted in the MC literature: In [13], the release of ions as SMs from a nanodevice (ND) via ligand- and voltage-gated ion channels was considered and, in [14], an MC testbed

¹We do not consider *control* in a control theory sense in this work. Instead, in this work, the term *controllable* is used to describe systems for which the output signal can be precisely tuned by adjusting the input signal.

was presented that utilized bacteria expressing light-driven ion pumps as externally controllable TXs for the release of protons, showing that ND-based optically controllable TXs are feasible in practice. While the authors of [13] and [14] focused on bit transmission as use case for MC, where ions are suitable as SMs, other applications such as TDD may require more complex SMs (e.g., drug molecules). Such SMs often cannot be transported by externally controllable transport proteins [15]. Therefore, to enable the release of these SMs, the cooperation of different transport proteins is required, as reported in [15] and [16]. Thus, in the proposed TX design, one type of protein operates as *energizing module* powering the second type of protein, which serves as *release module* for SMs. This design is entirely chemically implementable and can be applied in all environments where external light stimulation is possible. Additionally, the TX design can be adapted to a variety of SMs due to its modular structure. The energizing module facilitates the conversion of external light energy supplied by an light-emitting diode (LED) to a chemical concentration gradient between the intra- and extrav-vesicular space using light-driven ion pumps. This gradient then drives the release module which enables the release of SMs using ion/SM co-transporters. Some experimental work has been conducted on the incorporation of optically controllable, i.e., light-driven, transmembrane proteins into synthetic vesicle membranes [17], [18], showing that the synthesis of vesicle-based functionalized NDs is feasible.

Using light-responsive biological components is promising for providing a non-invasive methodology for exciting NDs in both experiments and future in-body applications, as visible light is able to penetrate human tissue [19]. Additionally, the excitation via light may allow for future inclusion of molecules exhibiting Förster resonance energy transmission or bioluminescence resonance energy transmission, which could theoretically act as relays for external or internal light sources, respectively [20], [21].

Another shortcoming of existing MC TX models based on NDs is that it is assumed that the TX consists of a single ND only. Experimentally, synthetic and natural vesicle concentrations are typically around 10^{10}ml^{-1} to 10^{13}ml^{-1} [22], [23] and the extraction, design, and analysis of single vesicles is infeasible due to their small size. Thus, considering TXs consisting of single NDs is unrealistic. In this work, we therefore consider *multiple vesicle systems (MVSs)*, which are TX systems consisting of many NDs. Due to the inherent randomness in the production process of vesicles, realistic vesicle-based NDs exhibit very heterogeneous behavior. It has been found that physical parameters such as the vesicle diameter and the permeability of the vesicle membrane vary among individual NDs [24], [25]. Other parameters that are expected to vary between vesicles, including the number of transmembrane proteins per vesicle, cannot be studied experimentally for single vesicles in a comprehensive and cost-efficient manner, and only estimates for the mean value among many vesicles exist [26]. In this work, we take into account this heterogeneous nature of vesicles in MVSs and evaluate the effect of random parameter values on the variance of SM release across different experiments. MVSs are compared to

the simplified *single vesicle system (SVS)* model, where the TX consists of exactly one ND, as commonly assumed in the literature.

Furthermore, in-body fluid systems, e.g., the bloodstream, and most chemical experimental systems rely on buffers for the stabilization of ion concentrations [27]. Whilst often disregarded in MC models, we also study the influence of this realistic environmental effect on the operation of our proposed TX design, i.e., we model the effect a buffer has on the ion concentration.

In this paper, we introduce a realistic externally controllable TX design based on multiple vesicular NDs that are functionalized for the controlled release of SMs by transmembrane proteins. The design based on two types of cooperative transmembrane transport proteins overcomes the existing drawbacks of previously proposed TXs by enabling the controlled release of SMs of various kinds. The combination of cooperating energizing and release modules for increased SM versatility, which has not been analyzed in the MC literature yet, increases the range of future applications of ND-based TXs. The proposed design might be suitable as a controllable TX for TDD or information transmission by encoding information in the change of the SM concentration over time.

The main contributions of this work are as follows:

- We investigate the design of modular, externally controllable TXs capable of releasing different types of SMs and operating under realistic environmental conditions.
- We propose a realistic system model to study the experimental deployment of such TXs comprising multiple NDs, where the inherent parameter randomness caused by the ND synthesis process is taken into account.
- We derive analytical and closed-form expressions for the SM release, analyze a possible practical realization of the proposed TX, and evaluate the impact of important system parameters on the SM release characteristics.

The proposed TX design was introduced in the conference version [1] of this paper. Here, we significantly extend [1] by considering realistic MVSs, deriving mathematical models for the reaction to the used light signal, and analyzing the effect of the inherent randomness of the system parameters known from experimental realizations of vesicle-based NDs.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In Section II, the proposed TX design is introduced in detail and a mathematical description as well as possible biological realizations for the energizing and release modules are provided. In Section III, an SVS is analyzed and corresponding solutions for the SVS model are derived in Section IV. In Section V, we extend the analyses to the MVS scenario and study the impact of parameter randomness. In Section VI, we compare the results obtained for different solution approaches. Finally, we draw conclusions in Section VII. Note that Table I provides an overview of the used variables and indices for the reader's convenience.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

In this section, we introduce the system model underlying our analyses. We first provide an overview of the proposed

TABLE I
OVERVIEW OF THE MOST RELEVANT VARIABLES

Index	Meaning
I	Ion transported by light-driven ion pumps and co-transporters. For the specific realization considered in Section III, $I \hat{=} H^+$.
S	Substrate transported by co-transporters.
E	Energizing module
R	Release module
L	Leakage
P	Light-driven ion pumps
Sym	Symporters (or antiporters)
Variable	Description
$C_{x,m}^X(t)$	Concentration of molecule $X \in \{I, S\}$ in the intra- or extravesicular volume ($x \in \{\text{in}, \text{out}\}$) of vesicle m over time t in mol m^{-3} .
$C_{x,0}^X$	Initial concentration of molecule X in the intra- or extravesicular volume ($x \in \{\text{in}, \text{out}\}$) of each vesicle.
C_0	Buffer molarity in mol m^{-3} .
$d_{\text{in},m}$	Inner vesicle diameter of vesicle m in m.
d_{mem}	Diameter of the vesicle membrane in m.
ν_{Sym}	Ratio of I and S molecules transported by a co-transporter.
$\gamma_{L,m}, \hat{\gamma}_{L,m}$	Effective rate of I leakage over the membrane and permeability coefficient of the membrane to I of vesicle m in $\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$ and m s^{-1} , respectively.
$\gamma_{P,m}^I, \hat{\gamma}_P$	Effective I transport rate of the energizing module in vesicle m and effective I transport rate of one light-driven I pump in mol s^{-1} and s^{-1} , respectively.
$\gamma_{\text{Sym},m}^X, \hat{\gamma}_{\text{Sym}}^X$	Effective $X \in \{I, S\}$ transport rate of the release module in vesicle m and effective X transport rate of one co-transport protein in mol s^{-1} and s^{-1} , respectively.
k_D	Buffer dissociation rate in mol m^{-3} .
K_m	Michaelis-Menten constant of the co-transporters in mol m^{-3} .
$l(t)$	Light signal with $l(t) \in \{0, 1\}$ over time t .
$i_{Y,m}^I(t)$	Flux of I caused by energizing or release module or leakage ($Y \in \{E, R, L\}$, respectively) in vesicle m over time t in $\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$.
$i_{R,m}^S(t)$	Flux of S caused by the release module in subsystem m over time t in $\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$.
ξ	Logarithmic threshold of symport start.
$C_{\xi,m}^I$	Symport threshold concentration, i.e., for symporter activity in mol m^{-3} .
$n_{x,m}$	Number of pumps ($x = P$) or co-transporters ($x = \text{Sym}$) in membrane of vesicle m .
$n_{\text{tot},m}$	Total number of functional proteins in membrane of vesicle m .
n_{exp}	Number of simulations.
n_{ves}	Number of vesicles/SVSs in an MVS.
n_{mod}	Number of simulated vesicles/SVSs in an MVS ($n_{\text{mod}} \leq n_{\text{ves}}$).
$\tau(t)$	Start time of the current signal phase at time t in s.
$t_i^{(x)}$	Time instants of pumping start ($x = 1$) and end ($x = 3$) in cycle i in s.
$t_{i,m}^{(x)}$	Time instants of symport start ($x = 2$) and end ($x = 4$) in cycle i in subsystem m in s.
$\theta_{\text{but}}(t)$	Flux attenuation factor caused by the buffer.
$\mathcal{V}_{x,m}, V_{x,m}$	Intra- ($x = \text{in}$) and extravesicular ($x = \text{out}$) spaces and their sizes in m^3 , respectively.
$\mathcal{V}_{\text{out,tot}}, V_{\text{out,tot}}$	Total extravesicular space and its size in m^3 , respectively.

MVSs and SVSs. Then, we introduce our modeling assumptions and derive a system of ordinary differential equations (ODEs) modeling the MVS. Additionally, we introduce a model for the buffer. Note that we focus on TX design in this work and therefore we do not consider a full end-to-end communication system. However, interested readers can find some preliminary results on the impact of SVSs on the end-to-end performance of MC systems in [28].

A. Multiple and Single Vesicle Systems

Figure 1a shows the proposed MVS containing $n_{\text{ves}} \in \mathbb{N}_0$ SVSs, i.e., single NDs featuring both energizing and release modules (right panels). Here, \mathbb{N}_0 denotes the set of non-negative integers. Note that each ND consists of exactly one functionalized vesicle. Therefore, the terms vesicle and

ND are interchangeable in this work. In Fig. 1, the SM (or substrate S) is depicted in orange. The ions I creating the gradients required for S release are depicted in gray. As shown in Fig. 1b, an MVS of volume $V_{\text{out,tot}}$ containing n_{ves} NDs can be compartmentalized into multiple SVSs consisting of the respective extravesicular space $\mathcal{V}_{\text{out},m}$ of size $V_{\text{out},m}$ and the respective intravesicular space $\mathcal{V}_{\text{in},m}$ of size $V_{\text{in},m}$, where $m \in \{1, 2, \dots, n_{\text{ves}}\}$. ND m has a spherical shape and a lipid or polymer membrane, which enables the encapsulation of SMs as cargo in $\mathcal{V}_{\text{in},m}$. The vesicle membrane is semi-permeable, i.e., it allows the translocation of some molecules between $\mathcal{V}_{\text{in},m}$ and $\mathcal{V}_{\text{out},m}$. The permeability of the membrane to a specific molecule depends on various factors, including the size of the molecule, with smaller molecules corresponding to a higher membrane permeability. The resulting net flux of ion

Fig. 1. General system model for the proposed ND-based TX. (a): Experimental set up of an MVS where n_{ves} NDs are contained in volume $V_{\text{out,tot}}$. (b): Detailed view of SVS $m \in \{1, 2, \dots, n_{\text{ves}}\}$ in the MVS. Variables $i_{E,m}^I$, $i_{L,m}^I$, $i_{R,m}^I$, and $i_{R,m}^S$ denote the flux of ion I caused by the energizing module, the leakage flux of I, and the flux of I and substrate S caused by the release module in vesicle m , respectively. The possible flux directions between the intravesicular volume, V_{in} , and the extravesicular volume, V_{out} , are indicated by arrows. The complex that the buffering ligand B may form with I is also depicted (complex of green and grey dots). The energizing and release module in each vesicle consists of *multiple* transmembrane transport proteins. Examples of suitable proteins and their transported cargo molecules are shown on the right-hand side. Abbreviations: AA = amino acid, NT = neurotransmitter. Created with BioRender.com.

I in outward direction over the membrane at time t is denoted by $i_{L,m}^I(t)$ and is also referred to as *leakage*. The substrate S generally is a larger molecule, e.g., an amino acid, for which the membrane typically has a very low permeability [29]. Therefore, we assume the leakage of S over the membrane to be negligible. Figure 1 also depicts the presence of buffer molecules B that may form a complex with I molecules in the aqueous solution.

The *energizing module* (depicted in blue in Fig. 1) is an energy conversion unit transforming the energy of photons to an electrochemical potential (i.e., a concentration and/or charge gradient²). The energizing module of ND m , consisting of $n_{p,m} \in \mathbb{N}_0$ light-driven ion pumping transmembrane proteins, actively transports ions I over the membrane. The influx caused by the energizing module is denoted by $i_{E,m}^I(t)$. This flux is unidirectional, as the pumps transport ions in a specific direction and the orientation of the pumps can be controlled during the insertion process in practice [17]. For the energizing module, several naturally occurring light-driven ion pumps emerge as potential chemical realizations, including proton (H^+) pumps (such as bacteriorhodopsin [14] and proteorhodopsin (PR) [30]), light-driven chloride (Cl^-) pumps [31], and light-driven sodium (Na^+) pumps [15].

The *release module* leverages the ion concentration gradient established by the energizing module as energy supply for the transport of the encapsulated substrate S across the ND membrane via $n_{\text{Sym},m} \in \mathbb{N}_0$ I/S co-transporters. In practice, two main groups of co-transporters exist: *Symporters* transport both molecules S and I in the same direction (see bottom left box on the right-hand side of Fig. 1), while *antiporters* act as exchangers, i.e., S is transported in the opposite direction as I (see bottom right box on the right-hand side of Fig. 1). The outfluxes of I and S caused by the release module are

denoted by $i_{R,m}^I(t)$ and $i_{R,m}^S(t)$, respectively. If symporters are used for the release module, an I gradient from $V_{\text{in},m}$ to $V_{\text{out},m}$ has to be established, such that S is transported from $V_{\text{in},m}$ to $V_{\text{out},m}$, i.e., released from the vesicle. An I concentration gradient in the opposite direction is required if antiporters are used. Hence, the required insertion direction of the light-driven I pumps depends on the type of co-transporter employed. For some co-transporters, a minimum I concentration gradient across the membrane is required to facilitate the transport [32]. We denote this threshold concentration by C_{ξ}^I , where ξ is the corresponding threshold. As the specific value and meaning of ξ depends on the choice of I, we will define ξ and C_{ξ}^I more rigorously for the concrete example considered in Section III. There is a vast number of natural, ion-driven co-transporters capable of transporting complex substrates. Biological examples include H^+ /amino acid symporters or Na^+ /amino acid symporters [33], [34], Na^+ /neurotransmitter symporters [15], and Cl^- /bicarbonate antiporters [35]. The choice of the specific energizing and release modules depends on the type of ion that is available, as both the light-driven pumps and co-transporters need to be able to transport it. For example, if the desired substrate is an amino acid, H^+ /amino acid symporters can be used in combination with H^+ pumps to establish the necessary H^+ gradient. Although there exist a number of possible combinations of energizing and release modules, the practical insertion of some transport proteins into the vesicle membrane may be challenging and many co-transporters lack a formal kinetic characterization. Thus, for the system analysis and the simulations, we will consider proteins that have already been successfully inserted into synthetic vesicle membranes and/or for which the transport kinetics are known.

Remark 1: Note that we could design a similar ND-based system capable of SM release upon light activation by leveraging modified mechanosensitive channels of large conductance (MscL), as described in [36]. MscL are mechanosensitive channels that serve as an exit valve for many types of cells in case of increased pressure [37]. Recently, different options for modulating the opening stimulus of MscL have been

²Note that other sources of energy could also be used to power the ion transport via the energizing module. For instance, adenosine triphosphate (ATP)-coupled transporters utilize the chemical energy stored in the molecule ATP as a driving force [15]. However, the energy for light-driven ion pumps can be readily supplied externally by an LED, and thus, light-driven energizing modules are considered exclusively in this work.

investigated and both light-sensitive and pH-sensitive channels have been reported [38]. A light-sensitive modification could serve as a release module in a similar ND design as proposed here. However, MscL are membrane channels, which are neither selective nor directional [39]. On the other hand, depending on the application of the ND, it may be undesirable to use large, non-specific membrane channels for SM release. Therefore, we consider only active and specific transport proteins as candidates for both the energizing and release module in this work. The use of passive gated channels as components for the release module would require a different mathematical model, which includes the concentration gradient of the substance permeating through the channel, as investigated in [13].

B. Modeling Assumptions

For the sake of mathematical tractability, we make the following assumptions. These assumptions are used to set up the system model in the following sections.

- (A1) We assume that in each SVS, the solution is well-stirred (e.g., in a stirred bioreactor [40]) and the total number of ions, N_m^I , and substrate molecules, N_m^S , are known. We assume that the concentrations of I and S are uniform in both $\mathcal{V}_{out,m}$ (e.g., due to stirring) and $\mathcal{V}_{in,m}$, as the diffusion of I and S is fast in comparison to their transport over the membrane: The expected range of diffusion coefficients of I and S is around $10^{-12}\text{m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$ to $10^{-9}\text{m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$ [41], [42], [43], which are large in comparison to typical vesicle diameters, which are around 20nm to 1000nm [44], and transport rates of the membrane proteins, which are around 10^{-3}s^{-1} to 10^3s^{-1} [45], [46].
- (A2) We assume that the light signal emitted by the LED, $l(t)$, is binary, i.e., $l(t) \in \{0, 1\}$ for all times t . Here, $l(t) = 1$ indicates that the LED is switched on, and $l(t) = 0$ means that the LED is switched off.
- (A3) We assume that the buffer molecule B only interacts with I, as it has a low affinity to other molecules. This assumption was verified experimentally for some standard buffers [47].
- (A4) We assume that the intra- and extravesicular volumes $\mathcal{V}_{in,m}$ and $\mathcal{V}_{out,m}$ of vesicle m only interact with each other and do not influence and are not influenced by any other $\mathcal{V}_{in,q}$ or $\mathcal{V}_{out,q}$ if $q \neq m$ for $q, m \in \{1, 2, \dots, n_{ves}\}$, i.e., we assume SVS independence. This assumption is justified for $V_{out,m} \gg V_{in,m}$, as the fluxes from and into the vesicle only generate very small changes in the extravesicular concentrations in this case.
- (A5) For the analytical expressions, we compartmentalize the total extravesicular volume $\mathcal{V}_{out,m}$ uniformly to obtain the extravesicular volumes of SVS m , i.e., $V_{out,m} = V_{out,tot}/n_{ves}$. This assumption is justified as $\mathcal{V}_{out,tot}$ is much larger than the sum of the size of the intravesicular volumes, i.e., $V_{out,tot} \gg \sum_{m=1}^{n_{ves}} V_{in,m}$, and the entire system is well stirred (see (A1)). In our baseline numerical simulations (see Section VI), we implement only one large extravesicular volume to validate this assumption.

Fig. 2. Working principle of a monoprotic buffer with buffering ligand B: Upon addition of ions (left panel), the change in the ion concentration is not as high as expected (middle panel) but lower due to the formation of ion-buffer ligand complexes IB (right panel). Created with BioRender.com.

C. System of ODEs Modeling the MVS

Using assumptions (A1)–(A4), the fluxes of I and S caused by the energizing module (comprising $n_{p,m}$ pumps), release module (comprising $n_{sym,m}$ symporters), and leakage can be used to set up a system of coupled ODEs describing the system kinetics for the proposed TX design for an SVS in the MVS as follows

$$V_{in,m} \frac{dC_{in,m}^I(t)}{dt} = i_{E,m}^I(t) - i_{L,m}^I(t) - i_{R,m}^I(t, C_{in,m}^S(t)), \quad (1)$$

$$V_{in,m} \frac{dC_{in,m}^S(t)}{dt} = -i_{R,m}^S(t, C_{in,m}^I(t)), \quad (2)$$

for all vesicles $m \in \{1, 2, \dots, n_{ves}\}$. Note that (1) and (2) are not coupled for different m , as we assume SVS independence (see (A4)), but they are coupled for each m . Here, $C_{in,m}^I(t)$, $C_{in,m}^S(t)$, $i_{E,m}^I(t)$, $i_{R,m}^I(t, C_{in,m}^S(t))$, and $i_{R,m}^S(t, C_{in,m}^I(t))$ are the intravesicular concentrations of I and S in mol m^{-3} , the influx of I caused by the energizing module, the outflux of I caused by the release module, and the outflux of S caused by the release module of ND m , respectively. All fluxes are measured in mol s^{-1} . If the release module consists of antiporters, the signs of the fluxes in (1) need to be switched. Note that the coupled system of ODEs in (1) and (2) only considers the concentrations in $\mathcal{V}_{in,m}$, but is sufficient to characterize the entire SVSs, as N_m^S and N_m^I are constant and known (see (A4)). The concentrations in $\mathcal{V}_{out,m}$ can thus be derived from those in $\mathcal{V}_{in,m}$, i.e., the I concentration $C_{out,m}^I(t) = (N_m^I - C_{in,m}^I(t)V_{in,m})/V_{out,m}$ and the S concentration $C_{out,m}^S(t) = (N_m^S - C_{in,m}^S(t)V_{in,m})/V_{out,m}$. According to (1) and (2), all SVSs can be analyzed *individually* before determining their joint impact on the extravesicular volume $\mathcal{V}_{out,tot} = \bigcup_{m=1}^{n_{ves}} \mathcal{V}_{out,m}$ by averaging the impact of the individual SVSs. To this end, the S concentration in $\mathcal{V}_{out,tot}$ can be obtained from the individual SVSs in subvolumes $\mathcal{V}_{out,m}$ as follows

$$C_{out,tot}^S(t) = \frac{1}{V_{out,tot}} \sum_{m=1}^{n_{ves}} V_{out,m} C_{out,m}^S(t) \stackrel{(A5)}{=} \frac{1}{n_{ves}} \sum_{m=1}^{n_{ves}} C_{out,m}^S(t). \quad (3)$$

D. Buffering Effects

The system of ODEs in (1) and (2) does not consider any buffering effects, yet. However, as metal ion or pH buffers are used in most experimental environments and are present, e.g., in in-body fluids [27], to stabilize ion concentrations, their effect has to be taken into account. Buffers function by reversibly binding or releasing ions in response to changes in the ion concentration, thereby avoiding changes in the free ion concentration in solution even when external factors would cause changes in this concentration. This principle is visualized in Fig. 2. We consider the following reversible reaction between I and a buffering ligand B

where IB, k_- , and k_+ are the complex formed by the ion and the ligand, the unbinding rate constant of I from B, and the binding rate constant of I to B, respectively. The dissociation constant of the ligand in equilibrium is $k_D = k_-/k_+$ in mol m⁻³. Using the mass action law [48], we obtain the concentration of I in the buffered system as follows

$$-\log(C^{\text{I}}) = -\log(k_D) + \log(C^{\text{B}}) - \log(C^{\text{IB}}), \quad (5)$$

where C^{X} denotes the concentration of molecule X. Generally, the buffer molarity is given by $C_0 = C^{\text{IB}} + C^{\text{B}}$ and remains constant. Thus, in equilibrium and for a given I concentration, C^{I} and C^{IB} can be deduced from (5). Note that for $\text{I} \hat{=} \text{H}^+$ ligand B would be a base and $-\log(C^{\text{H}^+}) = \text{pH}$. In this case, (5) specializes to the well-known Henderson-Hasselbalch equation [27]. We do not explicitly model the concentration of the buffer molecules in our system of ODEs, as the required extension of (1) and (2) to account for the concentration of four types of molecules becomes intractable. Instead, (5) will be incorporated into the numerical simulations of (1) and (2) and serve as a ground truth for the impact of the buffer. However, in our proposed analytical models, the impact of the buffer is approximated (see Section IV-D).

III. OPERATION AND ANALYSIS OF SINGLE VESICLE SYSTEM

This section investigates a specific realization of the proposed NDs using light-driven H^+ pumps (such as PR [30]) and H^+ symporters (e.g., PAT1 [33]) as energizing and release modules, respectively. Hence, $\text{I} \hat{=} \text{H}^+$ in the rest of this paper. As the use of light-driven H^+ pumps allows for a variety of possible release modules and, hence, different S (e.g., amino acids or neurotransmitters), we continue to treat S as a generic substrate molecule. For now, we concentrate on the SVS scenario. We begin by discussing the envisioned functionality of a SVS in Section III-A. In Section III-B, we discuss the different cycle types that can be observed upon illumination. Then, we propose expressions for the H^+ and S fluxes in Section III-C.

A. Operation of Single Vesicle System

In the following, while considering one SVS, we will drop vesicle index m to simplify the notation. To discuss

the functionality of the proposed ND in detail for the SVS, it is helpful to examine its behavior upon different external and internal stimuli. Hence, we consider the different states of the ND possible during one illumination cycle (shown in Fig. 3). A cycle describes a time period during which the light source is turned on and off exactly once. Each cycle consists of several phases, where a phase describes a time period during which a specific combination of system components (energizing module, release module, and leakage) is active. As the external light signal $l(t) \in \{0, 1\}$ can be chosen arbitrarily and usually consists of multiple illumination cycles, variable $i \in \mathbb{N}_0$ is used to index the cycles. Variables $t_i^{(j)}$ for $j \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ denote the end times of phase j in cycle i , as shown on the axis in Fig. 3a. First, we consider a regular cycle i consisting of the following four phases (P1)–(P4) (see Fig. 3a):

- (P1) *Leakage*: During the first cycle phase the ND is not illuminated and both types of transport proteins are inactive, i.e., only the leakage influences the H^+ flux ($|i_{\text{L}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)| \geq 0$, $i_{\text{E}}^{\text{H}^+}(t) = 0$, $i_{\text{R}}^{\text{H}^+}(t) = 0$).
- (P2) *Energizing module and leakage*: At $t_i^{(1)}$ the illumination begins and the proton pumps start transporting H^+ ($i_{\text{E}}^{\text{H}^+}(t) > 0$). Simultaneously, the increasing H^+ concentration in \mathcal{V}_{in} leads to an increasing pH difference between \mathcal{V}_{out} and \mathcal{V}_{in} yielding a leakage outflux of H^+ ($i_{\text{L}}^{\text{H}^+}(t) > 0$).
- (P3) *Energizing and release modules, and leakage*: When the threshold concentration for symporter activity within the vesicle, $C_{\xi}^{\text{H}^+}$, is reached at time $t_i^{(2)}$, the symporters in the release module become active. The symporters cause an additional outflux of H^+ and an outward transport of S ($i_{\text{R}}^{\text{H}^+}(t) > 0$, $i_{\text{R}}^{\text{S}}(t) > 0$, $i_{\text{E}}^{\text{H}^+}(t) > 0$, $i_{\text{L}}^{\text{H}^+}(t) > 0$).
- (P4) *Release module and leakage*: When the illumination ends at time $t_i^{(3)}$ but the intravesicular H^+ concentration is still above the threshold, i.e., $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t) > C_{\xi}^{\text{H}^+}$, the symporters remain active while the pumps stop transporting H^+ ($i_{\text{E}}^{\text{H}^+}(t) = 0$). During this cycle phase, both the symporters and the leakage cause H^+ outflux and S is transported outwards ($i_{\text{R}}^{\text{H}^+}(t) > 0$, $i_{\text{R}}^{\text{S}}(t) > 0$, $i_{\text{L}}^{\text{H}^+}(t) > 0$). When $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)$ falls below threshold $C_{\xi}^{\text{H}^+}$ at time $t_i^{(4)}$, cycle i ends and the next cycle $i+1$ starts. Note that, at the latest, a new cycle begins when the next illumination phase starts (even if the symport has not ended at that point).

Note that we assume $t_0^{(4)} = 0$, i.e., the first cycle ($i = 1$) starts at $t = 0$. While $t_i^{(1)}$ and $t_i^{(3)}$ depend on the external light signal $l(t)$, the symport start and end times, $t_i^{(2)}$ and $t_i^{(4)}$, depend exclusively on the H^+ concentrations and, thus, have to be calculated from $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)$, as shown in Section IV-C. The cycle index is required for the time variables limiting the cycle phases, but can be omitted for the fluxes and concentrations, which are defined for absolute time t . This is possible because the time variables for new cycles are monotonically increasing, i.e., $t_i^{(j')} \geq t_i^{(j)}$ where $j' > j$, and $t_{i'}^{(j)} \geq t_i^{(j)}$ where $i' > i$ (see Fig. 3). Generally, different types of illumination cycles can occur and the previously discussed sequence of phases holds only for regular cycles, i.e., cycles of type (a) in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. (a): A regular illumination cycle for an ND with $n_p = 3$ and $n_{\text{Sym}} = 2$ comprising four different cycle phases. The times $t_i^{(1)}$, $t_i^{(2)}$, $t_i^{(3)}$, and $t_i^{(4)}$ mark the transitions between two cycle phases. Here, $C_{\xi}^{\text{H}^+}$ indicates the symport threshold concentration. (b): A cycle without symporter activity. (c): Two subsequent cycles in between which the symport does not end. Parts of the image were created with BioRender.com.

For other cycle types, not all individual phases (P1)–(P4) do necessarily occur. These cycle types are examined in the following.

B. Other Types of Cycles

As mentioned previously, other types of cycles than type (a) can occur. Cycles of type (b) (Fig. 3b), for instance, occur when the illumination period in cycle i is too short to reach $C_{\xi}^{\text{H}^+}$. As the resulting symport duration, $t_i^{(4)} - t_i^{(2)}$, is 0 s, $t_i^{(2)} = t_i^{(3)} = t_i^{(4)}$ follows to ensure that the symport duration is correctly obtained and that all cycle limit times are properly defined and monotonically increasing.

Cycle type (c) occurs when the time between two illumination phases is too short for the symport of the first cycle to stop (see Fig. 3c). Hence, the time between the symport of two cycles, $t_{i+1}^{(4)} - t_i^{(4)}$, is set to 0 s. This holds for $t_i^{(4)} = t_{i+1}^{(1)} = t_{i+1}^{(2)}$. Hereby, it is ensured that all cycle phase limit times are properly defined.

C. Proton and Substrate Fluxes

Before deriving solutions for (1) and (2) in Sections IV-A and IV-B, mathematical models for the fluxes of H^+ and S are required.

1) *Energizing Module*: We assume that the light-driven proton pumps always operate at maximum effective rate as long as enough H^+ is available in \mathcal{V}_{out} during illumination. As the transport process of H^+ by light-driven pumps is rate-limited by one reaction, this assumption is well-justified [13], [49]. Consequently, the H^+ flux in mol s^{-1} caused by the energizing module comprising n_p proton pumps, $i_{\text{E}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)$, is defined as follows

$$i_{\text{E}}^{\text{H}^+}(t) = \frac{C_{\text{out}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)}{C_{\text{out},0}^{\text{H}^+}} \gamma_p \mathbb{1}_{\mathcal{X}}(I(t)), \quad (6)$$

where $C_{\text{out},0}^{\text{H}^+}$, γ_p , and $\mathbb{1}_{\mathcal{X}}(x)$ are the initial H^+ concentration in \mathcal{V}_{out} , the effective rate constant of H^+ for n_p proton pumps, and the indicator function, i.e., $\mathbb{1}_{\mathcal{X}}(x) = 1$ if $x \in \mathcal{X}$, and

$\mathbb{1}_{\mathcal{X}}(x) = 0$ otherwise, respectively. The effective pumping rate of one vesicle, $\gamma_p = \hat{\gamma}_p n_p / N_A$ in mol s^{-1} , depends on the effective pumping rate of one proton pump $\hat{\gamma}_p$ in s^{-1} , the number of pumps n_p , and the Avogadro constant $N_A = 6.022 \times 10^{23} \text{ mol}^{-1}$. Note that we neglect the delay between LED excitation and activation of the light-driven ion pumps, as this activation has been reported to be very fast (in the order of picoseconds for laser-flash induced photocycles) [49].

2) *Release Module*: We assume that the symporters are only active if the intravesicular H^+ concentration, $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)$, exceeds threshold $C_{\xi}^{\text{H}^+}$, based on the co-transporter kinetics described in the literature [32], [33]. The associated S and H^+ fluxes caused by the release module comprising n_{Sym} symporters can be described as follows

$$i_{\text{R}}^{\text{S}}(t) = \gamma_{\text{Sym}}^{\text{S}} \left(\frac{C_{\text{in}}^{\text{S}}(t)}{C_{\text{in}}^{\text{S}}(t) + K_m} \right) \mathbb{1}_{[C_{\xi}^{\text{H}^+}, \infty)}(C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)),$$

$$i_{\text{R}}^{\text{H}^+}(t) = \nu_{\text{Sym}} i_{\text{R}}^{\text{S}}(t), \quad (7)$$

where $\gamma_{\text{Sym}}^{\text{S}}$, K_m , and $\nu_{\text{Sym}} \in \mathbb{Q}$ are the effective S symport rate constant of one vesicle, the Michaelis-Menten constant in mol m^{-3} , and the ratio of H^+ to S molecules that are co-transported by a symporter, respectively. Here, \mathbb{Q} denotes the set of rational numbers. As ν_{Sym} is fixed and depends on the molecular structure of the co-transporter, the H^+ and S fluxes caused by the symporters can be deduced from one another by multiplication or division by ν_{Sym} . The effective symport rate of the release module in one ND is given by $\gamma_{\text{Sym}}^{\text{S}} = \hat{\gamma}_{\text{Sym}}^{\text{S}} n_{\text{Sym}} / N_A$ in mol s^{-1} , where $\hat{\gamma}_{\text{Sym}}^{\text{S}}$ is the effective S transport rate constant of one symporter in s^{-1} . In case of $I = \text{H}^+$, ξ corresponds to the pH threshold between \mathcal{V}_{in} and \mathcal{V}_{out} required for the start of the symport [32]. Thus, the threshold concentration required for the symport to start is $C_{\xi}^{\text{H}^+} = N^{\text{H}^+} / (V_{\text{out}} 10^{-\xi} + V_{\text{in}})$, where N^{H^+} is the total number of H^+ molecules in the SVS, and is obtained from the initial system pH and ξ . The expression for $C_{\xi}^{\text{H}^+}$ is obtained by solving the equation $\xi = \log(C_{\xi}^{\text{H}^+}) - \log(C_{\text{out},\xi}^{\text{H}^+})$, where $C_{\text{out},\xi}^{\text{H}^+} = (N^{\text{H}^+} - V_{\text{in}} C_{\xi}^{\text{H}^+}) / V_{\text{out}}$ is the extravesicular H^+ concentration

when the symport starts. In practice, it is expected that there is a delay before the symporters are activated, as establishing a concentration gradient large enough to power the symporters requires time. This delay depends on threshold ξ . Note that the symporters are naturally only active as long as S is available, i.e., $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{S}}(t) > 0$. The symporters become inactive when the vesicle has released all of its cargo. This state is referred to as substrate depletion.

3) *Leakage*: The H^+ flux caused by leakage of H^+ over the vesicle membrane is given as follows

$$j_{\text{L}}^{\text{H}^+}(t) = \gamma_{\text{L}} \left(C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t) - C_{\text{out}}^{\text{H}^+}(t) \right), \quad (8)$$

where $\gamma_{\text{L}} = \hat{\gamma}_{\text{L}} A_{\text{ves}}$ is the membrane permeability with respect to H^+ in $\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$. Here, $\hat{\gamma}_{\text{L}}$ is the permeability coefficient of H^+ for the vesicle membrane in m s^{-1} and A_{ves} is the outer surface area of the vesicle in m^2 . Note that the leakage flux scales linearly with the H^+ concentration gradient between \mathcal{V}_{in} and \mathcal{V}_{out} .

IV. ANALYTICAL SOLUTIONS

In this section, we derive analytical solutions for the concentrations of H^+ and S. First, an exact analytical solution is proposed, which is derived by solving the system of ODEs in (1) and (2) for each cycle phase identified in Section III and visualized in Fig. 3. As the exact analytical solution for cycle phases during which the release module is active (i.e., phases (P3) and (P4)) contains an integral that cannot be solved in closed-form, we also derive a closed-form approximation for the concentrations of H^+ and S for these phases. Moreover, we provide expressions for the calculation of the cycle-phase limits required for the application of both the exact analytical solution and the closed-form approximation. Finally, we propose an approximate method for incorporating the buffering effect into the analytical and closed-form solutions.

A. Exact Analytical Solution

For the analytical solution, ODEs (1) and (2) are considered separately for each cycle phase shown in Fig. 3. Before providing the cycle phase-dependent expressions for $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{S}}(t)$ and $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)$ in Proposition 1, we will first introduce several auxiliary variables. To indicate the start time of the current cycle phase and therefore differentiate between different cycle phases in the final expressions for $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{S}}(t)$ and $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)$, we introduce auxiliary variable $\tau(t)$,

$$\tau(t) = \max_{i,j} \{ t_i^{(j)} \mid t_i^{(j)} < t \}, \quad \forall j \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}. \quad (9)$$

Note that, as we define all cycle limits for absolute time, maximization over the cycles themselves is required to ensure that the current/most recent cycle is considered in (9). Using $\tau(t)$ to differentiate between different cycle phases, $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{S}}(t)$ and $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)$ can be expressed in a compact manner, using Proposition 1 (see below) and the cycle phase-dependent variables a and b

$$\begin{aligned} a &= j_{\text{L}}^a + j_{\text{P}}^a \mathbb{1}_{\{t_i^{(1)}, t_i^{(2)}\}}(\tau(t)), \\ b &= j_{\text{L}}^b + j_{\text{P}}^b \mathbb{1}_{\{t_i^{(1)}, t_i^{(2)}\}}(\tau(t)), \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

with auxiliary variables $j_{\text{L}}^a = \gamma_{\text{L}}(V_{\text{in}}^{-1} + V_{\text{out}}^{-1})$, $j_{\text{P}}^a = \gamma_{\text{P}}/(V_{\text{out}} C_{\text{out}}^{\text{H}^+})$, $j_{\text{L}}^b = -\gamma_{\text{L}} N^{\text{H}^+}/(V_{\text{out}} V_{\text{in}})$, and $j_{\text{P}}^b = j_{\text{P}}^a N^{\text{H}^+}/V_{\text{in}}$. Here, a and b capture the influence of the energizing module and the leakage on the intravesicular H^+ concentration. In the following, we use auxiliary function

$$f(t) := \frac{C_{\text{in},0}^{\text{S}}(t)}{K_{\text{m}}} e^{K_{\text{m}}^{-1} \left[C_{\text{in},0}^{\text{S}}(t) - \frac{\gamma_{\text{Sym}}^{\text{S}}}{V_{\text{in}}} (t - \tau(t)) \right]}, \quad (11)$$

where $C_{\text{in},0}^{\text{S}}(t) = C_{\text{in}}^{\text{S}}(\tau(t))$ denotes the initial intravesicular concentration of S in the current cycle phase.³

Proposition 1: The intravesicular concentration of S, $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{S}}(t)$, in (2) is obtained as follows for each phase j in cycle i

$$C_{\text{in}}^{\text{S}}(t) = \begin{cases} K_{\text{m}} W\{f(t)\}, & \text{if } t_i^{(2)} < t \leq t_i^{(4)}, \\ C_{\text{in},0}^{\text{S}}(t), & \text{if } t_{i-1}^{(4)} < t \leq t_i^{(1)}, \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

where $W\{\cdot\}$ denotes the Lambert W-function, defined by $W\{x\} \exp(W\{x\}) = x$.

The intravesicular H^+ concentration, $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)$, in (1) is obtained as follows for each phase j in cycle i

$$C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t) = \left[C_{\text{in},0}^{\text{H}^+}(t) - \alpha(\tau(t)) + \alpha(t) \right] e^{-a(t-\tau(t))}, \quad (13)$$

where $C_{\text{in},0}^{\text{H}^+}(t) = C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(\tau(t))$ is the initial intravesicular H^+ concentration of current cycle phase j and

$$\alpha(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{b}{a} e^{a(t-\tau(t))}, & \text{if } t_{i-1}^{(4)} < t \leq t_i^{(2)}, \\ \int_{\tau(t)}^t q(\omega) e^{a(\omega-\tau(\omega))} d\omega, & \text{if } t_i^{(2)} < t \leq t_i^{(4)}, \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

where $q(\omega) = \left(b - \frac{\gamma_{\text{Sym}}^{\text{H}^+}}{V_{\text{in}}} \frac{W\{f(\omega)\}}{W\{f(\omega)\}+1} \right)$.

Proof: Due to space limitations, we provide only a sketch of the proof for Proposition 1. We obtain the expression for $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{S}}(t)$ in (12) by inserting (7) into (2) and solving for $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{S}}(t)$. For a detailed derivation of the solution of the integral of a Michaelis-Menten equation including the emergence of the Lambert W-function, we refer the reader to [50, Sec. 2]. We then obtain (13) by inserting (12) and the expressions for the fluxes caused by the energizing (8) and release (7) modules as well as the leakage (8), respectively, into (1), resulting in

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dC_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)}{dt} &= -a C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t) + b - \mathbb{1}_{[C_{\xi}^{\text{H}^+}, \infty)}(C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)) \\ &\quad \times \frac{\gamma_{\text{Sym}}^{\text{H}^+}}{V_{\text{in}}} \frac{W\{f(t)\}}{W\{f(t)\}+1}. \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Finally, we solve ODE (15) for $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)$ by the commonly used approach of variation of parameters (see e.g., [51]). \square

While (12) and (13) provide an exact analytical solution for the concentrations of H^+ and S in an SVS, the integral in (14) cannot be solved in closed form and has to be evaluated numerically. Therefore, we derive a closed-form approximation that does not require numerical integration in the following.

³Note that $C_{\text{in},0}^{\text{S}} := C_{\text{in}}^{\text{S}}(0)$ denotes the initial intravesicular concentration of S in the system at $t = 0$.

B. Closed-Form Approximation

To obtain an approximate closed-form solution for $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)$ and $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{S}}(t)$, i.e., an analytical solution that circumvents the numerical integration in (14), we approximate the Michaelis-Menten term in (7) by piece-wise linearization. This leads to the approximation of the fluxes of S and H^+ through the release module in (7), i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} i_{\text{R}}^{\text{S}}(t) &\approx \gamma_{\text{Sym}}^{\text{S}} \mathbb{1}_{\mathbb{R}^+}(C_{\text{in}}^{\text{S}}(t)) \mathbb{1}_{[C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}, \infty)}(C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)) \\ &:= \gamma_{\text{Sym}}^{\text{S}}(t) \mathbb{1}_{[C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}, \infty)}(C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)), \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where \mathbb{R}^+ and $\gamma_{\text{Sym}}^{\text{S}}(t) = \gamma_{\text{Sym}}^{\text{S}} \mathbb{1}_{\mathbb{R}^+}(C_{\text{in}}^{\text{S}}(t))$ denote the set of positive real numbers and the time-dependent S transport rate, respectively. Approximation (16) is justified as long as $C_{\text{in},0}^{\text{S}} \gg K_{\text{m}}$ and assumes that the symporters operate with maximum rate as long as S is available and stop transporting when no S is left inside the vesicle. After inserting (16) into (2) and solving for $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{S}}(t)$, (12) simplifies to

$$C_{\text{in}}^{\text{S}}(t) = \begin{cases} C_{\text{in},0}^{\text{S}}(t), & \text{if } t_{i-1}^{(4)} < t \leq t_i^{(2)}, \\ C_{\text{in},0}^{\text{S}}(t) - \frac{\gamma_{\text{Sym}}^{\text{S}}(t)[t - \tau(t)]}{V_{\text{in}}}, & \text{if } t_i^{(2)} < t \leq t_i^{(4)}. \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

Similarly, (13) simplifies to

$$C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t) = a^{-1}b' - \left[C_{\text{in},0}^{\text{H}^+}(t) - a^{-1}b' \right] e^{-a(t-\tau(t))}, \quad (18)$$

where $b' = b + j_{\text{Sym}}^{\text{b}}(t) \mathbb{1}_{[t_i^{(2)}, t_i^{(3)}]}(\tau(t))$ with $j_{\text{Sym}}^{\text{b}}(t) = -\gamma_{\text{Sym}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)/V_{\text{in}}$. In contrast to (12) and (13), the closed-form approximations in (17) and (18) can be used to determine signal parameters such as the symporter start and end times, and the time of S depletion analytically. This is required for an adequate analytical description of the H^+ and S concentrations (upon external illumination of the ND) and the estimation of the duration of functionality of the ND.

The validity of the analytical solutions in (12) and (13) and the closed-form approximations in (17) and (18) will be verified by comparison to the numerical solution of ODEs (1) and (2) using a finite difference method (FDM) [52]. As FDM is exact for sufficiently small time steps Δt , we will consider the FDM simulations as the ground truth when discussing our results in Section VI.

C. Calculation of Cycle Phase Limits

As mentioned in Section III-A and shown in Fig. 3, the end times of the phases in cycle i are defined by $t_i^{(j)}$ for $j \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$. The times $t_i^{(1)}$ and $t_i^{(3)}$ for the start and the end of the illumination are determined by the external light signal $l(t)$. In contrast, the symport start and end times, $t_i^{(2)}$ and $t_i^{(4)}$, have to be calculated from the preceding cycle phases, i.e., phases (P2) and (P4), respectively. As (13) is not invertible, $t_i^{(2)}$ and $t_i^{(4)}$ cannot be calculated from the exact analytical solution. Instead, the closed-form approximation (18) can be solved for $t_i^{(2)}$ and $t_i^{(4)}$ during cycle phases (P1) and (P3), respectively, leading to approximate symport start and end times as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{t}_i^{(x)} &= -a^{-1} \log \left(C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+} - a^{-1}b' \right) \\ &+ a^{-1} \log \left(C_{\text{in},0}^{\text{H}^+}(t_i^{(x-1)}) - a^{-1}b' \right) + t_i^{(x-1)}, \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

for $x \in \{2, 4\}$. To ensure that all $t_i^{(j)}$ correspond to physically feasible values (i.e., that successive events such as pump and symporter activation occur in the correct orders visualized in Fig. 3), we need to ensure that $t_i^{(j)}$ is monotonically increasing. This is not guaranteed for cycle types where not all phases occur, i.e., cycles of types (b) and (c) (see Fig. 3 and Section III-B). For these cycle phases correctional clipping has to be applied to the values obtained from (19). Upon this clipping, the actual symport start times $t_i^{(2)}$ and end times $t_i^{(4)}$ can be obtained for all possible cycle types as follows

$$\begin{aligned} t_i^{(2)} &= \max(\min(t_i^{(1)}, \tilde{t}_i^{(2)}, t_i^{(3)}), \\ t_i^{(4)} &= \max(\min(t_i^{(3)}, \tilde{t}_i^{(2)}, t_{i+1}^{(1)}). \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

For example, in case of a cycle of type (b) (see Fig. 3b), where no symporter activity is observed during the time of illumination, the symport start time, $t_i^{(2)}$, will be set to $t_i^{(3)}$ according to (20), as the theoretically calculated symport start time $\tilde{t}_i^{(2)}$ is not lower than the end time of illumination, $t_i^{(3)}$. Similarly, $t_i^{(4)}$ is set to $t_{i+1}^{(1)}$ because it would otherwise yield a physically infeasible value.

D. Influence of Buffer

We assume that the system is immersed in a buffer solution (see Section II-B) with total buffer molarity C_0 in both volumes V_{in} and V_{out} . Equation (5) can be used to calculate the pH of a monoprotic buffer using the concentration of acid and base molecules and, thus, facilitates the explicit modeling of the impact of a buffer. Therefore, we incorporate (5) into the numerical FDM solution as the ground truth for the impact of the buffer. However, (5) is not amenable to analytical solution as its incorporation into (1) and (2) would lead to an intractable system of ODEs. Thus, we approximate the effect of the buffer solution as an attenuation of the H^+ flux from one volume to another as proposed in [53]. This means that the presence of a buffer decreases the change of ion concentration induced by an influx of ions in comparison to an unbuffered system. The approach from [53] simply scales the flux rates of H^+ , i.e., γ_{L} , γ_{P} , and $\gamma_{\text{Sym}}^{\text{H}^+}$, by a factor $\vartheta_{\text{buf}}(t) = k_{\text{D}}C_0(C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t) + k_{\text{D}})^{-2}$ [54, Eq. (12)]. This attenuation factor depends on the inner H^+ concentration $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)$ and therefore varies over time. Incorporating the time-variant attenuation factor $\vartheta_{\text{buf}}(t)$ into (1) and (2) would thus lead to a system of non-linear ODEs. To avoid this, we assume that during *each cycle phase* the attenuation factor $\vartheta_{\text{buf}}(t)$ remains constant and is computed using the initial intravesicular H^+ concentration of the cycle phase, $C_{\text{in},0}^{\text{H}^+}(t) = C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(\tau(t))$, i.e.,

$$\vartheta_{\text{buf}}(\tau(t)) \approx k_{\text{D}}C_0(C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(\tau(t)) + k_{\text{D}})^{-2}. \quad (21)$$

Note that only values $\vartheta_{\text{buf}}(\tau(t)) > 1$ are valid as other values correspond to an unbuffered scenario, which does not require flux attenuation. Scaling the H^+ fluxes in (1) and (2) with (21) leads to a system of ODEs with a tractable solution for all cycle phases. In fact, the obtained solution is similar to (17) and (18) and simply uses rescaled auxiliary variables $j_Y^{x*} = j_Y^x \vartheta_{\text{buf}}(\tau(t))^{-1}$ for $x \in \{a, b\}$ and $Y \in \{\text{L}, \text{P}, \text{Sym}\}$. In our simulations, we will validate approximation (21) by

Fig. 4. Visualization of the considered random processes and distributions underlying the vesicle production process and influencing the vesicle diameter (left), the number of pumps and symporters per vesicle (center), and the membrane permeability to H^+ (right). Created with BioRender.com.

comparison to our numerical FDM solution, where the impact of the buffer is explicitly modelled using (5).

V. EXTENSION TO MULTIPLE VESICLE SYSTEM

In this section, we expand the previous analyses of the SVS to an MVS consisting of n_{ves} NDs. To accurately model the MVS, we consider the random distribution of several vesicle parameters. Therefore, we introduce random variables sampled from different random distributions to accurately model varying inner vesicle diameters d_{in} , numbers of pumps n_P , numbers of symporters n_{Sym} , and membrane permeabilities $\hat{\gamma}_L$, respectively. Then, we analyze the obtained MVS model mathematically and investigate its behavior in comparison to an SVS with mean parameter values and the behavior of multiple MVSs across multiple experiments.

A. Parameter Randomness

In MVSs, multiple vesicles are active and contribute to the release of SMs (see Fig. 1a). In realistic experiments, different vesicle parameters such as the vesicle diameter and the number of membrane proteins per vesicle are not deterministic but randomly distributed [24]. This parameter randomness is unavoidable and mostly introduced during the vesicle production process [55]. We discuss three practically relevant parameters and their distributions (see Fig. 4) in the following.⁴

1) *Inner Vesicle Diameter*: The distribution of the inner vesicle diameter, $d_{\text{in},m}$, can be inferred from experiments and is illustrated on the left-hand side of Fig. 4. As the vesicle membrane consists of lipids or polymers with characteristic lengths, the membrane thickness, d_{mem} , is typically considered to be deterministic.⁵ Therefore, variations of $d_{\text{in},m}$ lead to different vesicle sizes. The actual diameter of the vesicles varies and it can be shown experimentally that the inner vesicle

⁴Note that if the parameters of all n_{ves} vesicles within an MVS were deterministic and identical, the MVS would collapse to an SVS according to (3).

⁵Note that the insertion of proteins into lipid or polymer membranes may locally impact membrane thickness [56], [57]. However, for our analysis, we neglect these local fluctuations and focus instead on comparative properties across distinct vesicles. Similarly, effects such as lateral fluidity, packing, and spontaneous curvature caused by both membrane constituent molecules and inserted proteins can impact membrane properties, including their permeability [58], [59]. For the sake of conciseness, we also disregard these local effects in this work.

diameter of synthetic liposomes and polymersomes follows a shifted Log-normal distribution [60].

Consequently, to account for this randomness of the inner vesicle diameter, $d_{\text{in},m}$, we assume $d_{\text{in},m} \sim \mathcal{LN}(x; l_{\text{ves}}, \sigma_{\text{ves}}, \mu_{\text{ves}})$ with

$$f_{\mathcal{LN}}(x, \sigma_{\text{ves}}, \mu_{\text{ves}}) = \frac{e^{-(\ln(x-l_{\text{ves}})-\mu_{\text{ves}})^2/2\sigma_{\text{ves}}^2}}{(x-l_{\text{ves}})\sigma_{\text{ves}}\sqrt{2\pi}} \times \mathbb{1}_{(l_{\text{ves}}, +\infty)}\{x\}, \quad (22)$$

for $x > l_{\text{ves}}$, where $\mathcal{LN}(x; l_{\text{ves}}, \sigma_{\text{ves}}, \mu_{\text{ves}})$ denotes the Log-normal distribution with shaping parameter $\sigma_{\text{ves}} \in \mathbb{R}^+$, location parameter $\mu_{\text{ves}} \in \mathbb{R}$, shift parameter $l_{\text{ves}} \in \mathbb{R}$, and probability density function $f_{\mathcal{LN}}(\cdot)$. In (22), $\ln(\cdot)$ denotes the natural logarithm. Note that σ_{ves} and μ_{ves} correspond to the standard deviation and mean of the underlying Normal distribution of random variable $\ln(d_{\text{in},m})$, respectively. Parameters σ_{ves} and μ_{ves} have to be obtained from experimental data and depend on various factors such as the lipid or polymer chosen for the membrane and the vesicle production process.

2) *Number of Pumps and Symporters*: Another source of randomness is the number of pumps and symporters per vesicle, whose ratio is expected to vary between individual NDs in MVSs (see center panel of Fig. 4). However, to the best of our knowledge, there is no detailed description for the inherent randomness of protein reconstitution, yet. Therefore, we assume that the total number of proteins, $n_{\text{tot},m} = \lfloor \pi(d_{\text{in},m} + d_{\text{mem}})^2 \rho_{\text{ves}} \rfloor$, where $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ is the floor function yielding the greatest integer lower than or equal to its argument, depends linearly on the surface area of vesicle m and the average density of proteins on the surface of a vesicle ρ_{ves} , where density ρ_{ves} can be inferred from experimental data. There are thus $n_{\text{tot},m} = n_{P,m} + n_{\text{Sym},m}$ slots on the surface of each vesicle that may contain either a pump or a symporter, i.e., $n_{P,m}$ and $n_{\text{Sym},m}$ are dependent random variables. Therefore, we assume that the number of pumps is given by a Binomial distribution, i.e., $n_{P,m} \sim \text{Binom}(n_{\text{tot},m}, p_P)$ with

$$f_{\text{Binom}}(n_{\text{tot},m}, p_P) = \binom{n_{\text{tot},m}}{k} p_P^k (1-p_P)^{n_{\text{tot},m}-k}, \quad (23)$$

$$n_{\text{Sym},m} = n_{\text{tot},m} - n_{P,m},$$

where $\text{Binom}(k; n_{\text{tot},m}, p_P)$ denotes the Binomial distribution with probability density function f_{Binom} for $n_{\text{tot},m}$ samples and probability $p_P \in [0, 1]$, and $d_{\text{in},m}$ is sampled according to (22).

3) *Membrane Permeability*: The third practically relevant source of randomness we consider is the permeability coefficient of H^+ , as shown on the right-hand side of Fig. 4. Recently, single vesicle analyses have shown that the permeability coefficient of lipid membranes with respect to H^+ , $\hat{\gamma}_{L,m}$, is not deterministic but rather randomly distributed over several orders of magnitude [25]. For some lipids the coefficients seem to be correlated with the vesicle diameter, while for others such dependency cannot be observed. As these analyses are tedious to carry out, they cover only low numbers of samples. Thus, it is difficult to estimate the actual random distribution of permeability coefficients $\hat{\gamma}_{L,m}$ from the available experimental data. We therefore assume that $\ln(\hat{\gamma}_{L,m})$ is sampled from a truncated normal distribution (see right-hand

side of Fig. 4) where the truncation ensures that the sampled values remain in a physically feasible range. We assume that $\ln(\hat{\gamma}_{L,m})$ is statistically independent from $d_{in,m}$ and therefore obtain $\ln(\hat{\gamma}_{L,m}) \sim \mathcal{TN}(x; \mu_L, \sigma_L, l_L, u_L)$ with

$$f_{\mathcal{TN}}(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sigma_L \sqrt{\pi}} \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{(x-\mu_L)^2}{2\sigma_L^2}\right)}{\operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{u_L-\mu_L}{\sigma_L \sqrt{2}}\right) - \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{l_L-\mu_L}{\sigma_L \sqrt{2}}\right)}, & \text{if } l_L < x < u_L, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

where $\mathcal{TN}(x; \mu_L, \sigma_L, l_L, u_L)$ denotes the truncated Normal distribution with probability density function $f_{\mathcal{TN}}$. Here, $\mu_L, \sigma_L, l_L \in \mathbb{R}$, and $u_L \in \mathbb{R}$ (with $u_L > l_L$) are the mean and standard deviation of the underlying non-truncated Normal distribution and the lower and upper truncation limits, respectively. Therefore, $\hat{\gamma}_{L,m}$ is distributed in a truncated Log-normal fashion according to (24). In (24), $\operatorname{erf}(\cdot)$ denotes the Gaussian error function.

B. Mathematical Analysis of MVS

In the proposed MVS model, individual vesicles with randomly varying parameters are modeled as SVSs according to the assumption of SVS independence (A4). To validate (A4), we utilize the extravesicular H^+ concentration in $\mathcal{V}_{out,tot}$ in the FDM simulations, i.e., we average the $C_{out,m}^{H^+}(t)$ of all SVSs, i.e., $C_{out,tot}^{H^+}(t) = 1/n_{ves} \sum_{m=1}^{n_{ves}} C_{out,m}^{H^+}(t)$. The FDM, thus, serves as a baseline for our analytical approximations which are based on the assumption that $\mathcal{V}_{out,tot}$ is a well-mixed medium. In order to characterize the behavior of an MVS, we provide the following theorems.

Theorem 1: Given an MVS that contains $n_{ves} > 1$ vesicles where the parameter d_{in} , n_P , n_{Sym} , and $\hat{\gamma}_L$ are randomly distributed with a variance larger than 0, its behavior cannot be modeled by an SVS with the mean parameter values \bar{d}_{in} , \bar{n}_P , \bar{n}_{Sym} , and $\bar{\hat{\gamma}}_L$.

Proof: See Section A.□

If we consider multiple MVSs (e.g., representing different experimental batches) with the same underlying random distributions of n_P , d_{in} , and $\hat{\gamma}_L$, we can calculate the unbiased estimate of the inter-experiment variance among the MVSs. This variance indicates how similar different experimental batches behave, i.e., how reproducible an experiment is. Therefore, we define the inter-experiment variance for a signal, e.g., the extravesicular S concentration, as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \operatorname{Var}\{C_{out}^S(t)\} &= \frac{1}{n_{exp} - 1} \sum_{q=1}^{n_{exp}} \left(C_{out,tot,q}^S(t) - \frac{1}{n_{exp}} \sum_{q'=1}^{n_{exp}} C_{out,tot,q'}^S(t) \right)^2 \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

where variable q indicates the q -th experiment. In (25), $\frac{1}{n_{exp}} \sum_{q'=1}^{n_{exp}} C_{out,tot,q'}^S(t)$ constitutes the inter-experiment average. We make the following observation regarding the inter-experiment variance:

Theorem 2: Given multiple MVSs with the same underlying distributions of d_{in} , n_P , and $\hat{\gamma}_L$, $\operatorname{Var}\{C_{out}^S(t)\}$ in (25) approaches

0 as the number of vesicles in the MVS tends to infinity ($n_{ves} \rightarrow \infty$).

Proof: Given (A5), $C_{out,tot,q}^S(t)$ is the empirical average over $C_{out,m,q}^S(t)$ per experiment q . As n_{ves} tends to infinity, we obtain $\lim_{n_{ves} \rightarrow \infty} C_{out,tot,q}^S(t) = \mathcal{E}\{C_{out,m}^S(t)\}$. As the vesicle parameters are sampled from the same distributions among all experiments, $\mathcal{E}\{C_{out,m}^S(t)\}$ is independent of q . Consequently, the argument in the sum over q in (25) becomes 0 and so does $\operatorname{Var}\{C_{out}^S(t)\}$.□

VI. CHARACTERIZATION OF ND-BASED MC TXS

In this section, the results for both the SVS and the MVS obtained for the exact analytical solution (12) and (13) and the closed-form approximation (17) and (18) are presented and compared to the ground truth, which is numerically obtained by FDM. First, we investigate the impact of the buffer molarity on the dynamics of the energizing module of an SVS. Then, the functionality of the entire SVS is examined for varying ratios of the numbers of pumps and symporters. As the transport rate of proteins cannot be changed straightforwardly, the numbers of pumps and symporters in the vesicle membrane are important design parameters since they directly scale the fluxes of I and S (see (6) and (7)). Lastly, for the SVS, the influence of different transport rates of symporters (corresponding to different symporter types) and different membrane permeabilities on the release of S for different illumination durations is discussed.

For the analysis of MVSs, the differences among the vesicles within one experiment are studied in comparison to the joint behavior of an MVS over several experimental realizations. Then, a sensitivity analysis is conducted to determine critical experimental parameters that heavily influence the system behavior upon variation.

If not specified otherwise, all simulations are conducted using the default parameters shown in Table II. These default values are chosen to be in line with experimental data, if available. The time step Δt is relevant for the numerical FDM baseline, which requires time discretization.

A. Energizing Module: Evaluation of the Impact of the Buffer

In order to assess the functionality of the proposed H^+ -based energizing module under varying experimental conditions, in our first evaluation, we consider an ND without release module, i.e., $n_{Sym} = 0$, for different buffer molarities C_0 . Figure 5 shows $C_{in}^{H^+}(t)$ as a function of time t for various buffer concentrations C_0 as obtained from the exact analytical solution (13) (green), the approximate solution (18) (orange), and the numerical baseline (blue). The results were obtained for 600 s of continuous illumination followed by 600 s without illumination, as indicated by the shading in Fig. 5. We observe that the general signal shapes are in agreement with experimental data from the literature employing a similar setup using light-driven H^+ pumps (compare Fig. 5 with [18, Fig. 3]). In both our simulations and the experimental measurements, illumination causes an increase of $C_{in}^{H^+}(t)$ (i.e., a decrease in the intravesicular pH) that approaches saturation

TABLE II
DEFAULT PARAMETERS FOR THE EVALUATIONS

Parameter	Value	Ref.	Parameter	Value	Ref.	Parameter	Value	Ref.
Δt	1×10^{-2} s		K_m	1.3×10^{-2} mol m ⁻³	[61]	n_{exp}	10	
$C_{\text{in},0}^S$	300 mol m ⁻³	*	ν_{Sym}	3	[34]	μ_{ves}	$4.16 \log(\text{nm})$	‡
C_0	20 mol m ⁻³	[17]	$\hat{\gamma}_{\text{Sym}}^S$	0.006 s ⁻¹	[45]	σ_{ves}	0.62	‡
k_D	6.2×10^{-5} mol m ⁻³	[27]	n_{Sym}	30	[17]	l_{ves}	39.74 nm	‡
d_{in}	87 nm	[44]	γ_L	3×10^{-6} m s ⁻¹	[62]	ρ_{tot}	0.168 nm ⁻²	
d_{mem}	14 nm	[44]	$\hat{\gamma}_P$	0.03 s ⁻¹	[30]	p_P	4/7	
$V_{\text{out,tot}}$	1×10^{-6} m ³	[17]	n_P	40	[17]	μ_L	-5.52	
$C_{\text{in},0}^{\text{H}^+}$	3.98×10^{-5} mol m ⁻³	**	ξ	0.015	†	σ_L	0.25	
$C_{\text{out},0}^{\text{H}^+}$	3.98×10^{-5} mol m ⁻³	**	n_{ves}	10^{11}	[26]	l_L	-5.77	
			n_{mod}	100		u_L	-5.27	

* Expected concentration that can be loaded into vesicles based on reported, similarly high encapsulation concentrations [63].

** Corresponds to a pH of 7.4, which is standard for some commonly used buffers [17].

† Rough estimate for a symporter that is active at the resting membrane potential of a cell.

‡ Value is obtained from curve fitting on experimental data (refer to Section VI-D for details).

Fig. 5. Intravesicular H^+ concentration, $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)$, (bottom) for one illumination period without release module, i.e., $n_{\text{Sym}} = 0$, and for varying buffer molarities C_0 . Results obtained with FDM (blue), the exact analytical solution (13) (green), and the approximate analytical solution (18) (orange) are shown as a function of time t . The light signal $l(t)$ (red) is shown on the top. Shaded gray areas indicate times during which $l(t) = 1$. The black line shows the H^+ concentration, $C_{\text{in,eq}}^{\text{H}^+}$, where in- and outflux to/from the vesicle are in equilibrium while $l(t) = 1$.

exponentially. Dark phases similarly cause a return to the initial value of $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)$. This suggests that our developed system model successfully captures the behavior of the envisioned ND. Figure 5 also highlights the importance of modeling buffering effects, as the system dynamics of a buffered system ($C_0 > 0$ mol m⁻³) clearly differ from those of an unbuffered system ($C_0 = 0$ mol m⁻³). In fact, the buffer introduces a time delay before the equilibrium concentration is reached. Similarly, increasing the buffer molarity also increases the delay before the symporters are activated, as their activation requires a specific intravesicular H^+ concentration for the concentration gradient across the membrane to pass threshold ξ . We observe that a higher buffer molarity causes a smaller slope of $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)$ during both illumination ($l(t) = 1$) and no illumination ($l(t) = 0$). As expected, for increasing buffer molarity, the H^+ in- and outfluxes are more attenuated by the buffer and therefore the rate of change in $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)$ is smaller. It

is noteworthy that, for all buffer molarities, $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)$ approaches the same value for sufficiently long illumination durations. This value is the dynamic equilibrium concentration $C_{\text{in,eq}}^{\text{H}^+}$ (black line in Fig. 5), where the influx $i_{\text{E}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)$ caused by the pumps is equal to the outflux $i_{\text{L}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)$ caused by the leakage. As all H^+ molecules entering or leaving \mathcal{V}_{in} are equally buffered, $C_{\text{in,eq}}^{\text{H}^+}$ is unaffected by the buffer molarity. However, as can be observed in Fig. 5, the speed at which the equilibrium is reached changes, e.g., the curve for $C_0 = 100$ mol m⁻³ does not reach $C_{\text{in,eq}}^{\text{H}^+}$ as the illumination period considered in Fig. 5 is too short. Generally, Fig. 5 shows that the analytical solutions are in good agreement with the numerical baseline. Interestingly, the closed-form approximation is very accurate while entailing much lower computational costs compared to the other solutions. Only when the changes in $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)$ are large in the buffered scenario, e.g., for low buffer molarities (e.g., $C_0 = 10$ mol m⁻³), small deviations between the analytical solutions and the FDM solution can be observed. The reason for these deviations is the phase-wise constant attenuation factor $\vartheta_{\text{bur}}(\tau(t))$ in (21). As long phases typically lead to substantial changes in $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)$ due to H^+ in- or outflux, the assumption of constant $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)$ used for calculating $\vartheta_{\text{bur}}(\tau(t))$ in (21) becomes invalid. The deviation decreases again when $C_{\text{in,eq}}^{\text{H}^+}$ is reached as no $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)$ changes occur anymore as long as the cycle phase does not change. Conclusively, we note that the buffer molarity of the system determines how responsive the energizing module is with respect to changes in the external stimulus. In particular, higher buffer molarities introduce a latency to the stimulus response, while low buffer molarities lead to a more responsive system.

B. Energizing and Release Module: Evaluation of the ND Functionality

1) *Accurate Analytical Solutions for All Cycle Types*: In comparison to Fig. 5, which showed a scenario without release

Fig. 6. Intravesicular H^+ concentration (middle panel) and extravesicular S concentration (bottom panel) for different cycle types (a), (b), and (c) and solution approaches. The active system components during each cycle phase are shown on top (green: proton pumps, orange: symporters, blue: leakage) and dashed lines indicate cycle phase limits. The intravesicular H^+ concentration required for symport activation, $C_\xi^{H^+}$, is shown by the horizontal black line in the middle panel.

modules, we now consider a system with $n_{Sym} > 0$. **Figure 6** shows the system response to a light signal chosen such that all three cycle types (a)–(c) occur (see **Fig. 3**). Evidently, for all cycles types, the analytical and numerical solutions are in good agreement. This indicates that our model adequately captures the system behavior for different light signal patterns. The first illumination phase in **Fig. 6** is not long enough for $C_\xi^{H^+}$ to be reached, thus the symporters remain inactive and a cycle of type (b) occurs. The symporter inactivity can also be observed in the amount of released S (bottom panel of **Fig. 6**), which remains unchanged during $t < 50$ s. For future experiments, it is necessary to carefully design the light signal in such a way that cycles of type (b) (see **Fig. 3b**) are avoided, as the goal of SM release is not achieved. The illumination phase of cycle $i = 2$ is of similar length to that of cycle $i = 1$, but due to a higher initial concentration $C_{in,0}^{H^+}(t = t_2^{(1)})$ when cycle $i = 2$ starts at $t = 50$ s, the symporters become active during this cycle. We observe that the slope of $C_{in}^{H^+}(t)$ decreases and that $C_{out}^S(t)$ increases linearly when the symporters are active, as $i_R^S(t) > 0$ for $C_{in}^{H^+}(t) > C_\xi^{H^+}$. During the subsequent dark phase ($t \in [80, 110]$ s), the symporters become inactive at $t \approx 100$ s (see sudden stop of increase in $C_{out}^S(t)$). Therefore, cycle $i = 2$ is a regular cycle of type (a). The following cycles $i = 3$ and 4 are of type (c) as the dark phase ($t \in [140, 150]$ s) between the illumination phases is too short to stop the symporter activity (see continuous increase in $C_{out}^S(t)$ for $t > 110$ s). **Figure 5** shows that our derived analytical solutions are in good agreement with the numerical baseline for all cycle types and are, therefore, expected to model the system at hand reliably.

2) Impact of the Composition of the Membrane Proteins Over Time: **Figure 7** shows $C_{in}^{H^+}(t)$, $C_{out}^S(t)$, and the outflux of S caused by the release module, $i_R^S(t)$, for different ratios of n_p and n_{Sym} , while the total number of membrane proteins n_{tot} remains constant. Generally, we observe that a smaller number of symporters leads to larger $C_{in}^{H^+}(t)$ during the illumination phases due to a lower symport-caused H^+ outflux. Similarly, the influence of a lower number of symporters is

Fig. 7. Intravesicular H^+ concentration, extravesicular S concentration, and the outflux of S caused by the symporters over multiple illumination cycles for varying protein ratios n_p/n_{Sym} and $C_{in,0}^S = 3.14 \text{ mol m}^{-3}$. The arrows indicate decreasing n_p/n_{Sym} . Shaded gray areas indicate times during which $l(t) = 1$.

also observable from the smaller slope of $C_{out}^S(t)$ (see center panel of **Fig. 7**) or, equivalently, from the lower amplitude of $i_R^S(t)$ during illumination periods (bottom panel of **Fig. 7**). However, the higher peaks of $C_{in}^{H^+}(t)$ for smaller n_{Sym} lead to a longer symport duration, $t_i^{(4)} - t_i^{(2)}$, in each cycle as shown by the increasing width of the rectangles in $i_R^S(t)$ for decreasing n_{Sym} . These observations lead to the conclusion that a lower number of symporters does not necessarily correlate with an overall lower amount of released S (which is proportional to the area of the rectangles in $i_R^S(t)$) as a lower outflux rate causes longer symport durations. For the case $n_p/n_{Sym} = 1$, we also observe the effect of substrate depletion, i.e., $C_{in}^S(t)$ approaches 0, in **Fig. 7**. To investigate this phenomenon, we have chosen a low $C_{in,0}^S = 3.14 \text{ mol m}^{-3}$ for which substrate depletion takes place at around $t = 6500$ s. However, in practice, larger $C_{in,0}^S$ are achievable and should be used to increase the longevity of the ND (see **Table II**). For $n_p/n_{Sym} = 4/3$, the substrate is depleted even earlier as evident from the fact that $i_R^S(t) = 0$ for all plotted times $t > 6350$ s (highlighted in red in **Fig. 7**). On the other hand, substrate depletion is not reached during the simulation time for $n_p/n_{Sym} = 3/4$. Consequently, the rectangular signal shape of $i_R^S(t)$ is maintained until the end of the simulation. We also note that during substrate depletion, the accuracy of the approximate solution (17) decreases (see mismatch between the blue and orange curves in the bottom panel of **Fig. 7** for $n_p = n_{Sym}$) as the linear approximation is not able to capture the decrease in the symport rate characteristic for Michaelis-Menten kinetics (see (7) for $C_{in}^S(t) \ll K_m$). In contrast, the exact analytical solution (13) is able to capture this effect, and the slight deviations from the numerical

Fig. 8. Top: Symport duration over the illumination duration ($t^{(1)} = 0$ s) for different symport and leakage rates. Bottom: Corresponding $C_{\text{out}}^S(t)$ during the illumination period. The vertical black line marks the minimum illumination time needed for symporter activity.

baseline are attributed to the finite time resolution in the numerical integration for obtaining $\alpha(t)$ in (14). Note that the light signal in Fig. 7 may be interpreted as a modulated transmit signal for concentration shift keying. Since the difference in $i_R^S(t)$ during illumination and dark phases mimics the shape of the optical transmit signal, the resulting signal may be suitable for encoding information. Generally, Fig. 7 shows that the ratio n_p/n_{Sym} is an important design parameter of the ND. For example, if the envisioned use case of the ND requires a prolonged, sustained release of S upon illumination (wide rectangles), large n_p/n_{Sym} should be chosen, while for shorter temporal responses to the external stimuli (narrow rectangles) small n_p/n_{Sym} are favorable.

C. Estimation of Substrate Release

In order to utilize the proposed ND for applications such as TDD or information transmission, it is pivotal to study the dynamics of the finite amount of S molecules released from the vesicle. One important variable in this context is the expected number of released S in response to a specific illumination duration, which scales linearly with the expected duration of symport during an illumination cycle (while $C_{\text{in}}^S(t) \gg K_m$). The closed-form expression (19) allows for the estimation of the start $t^{(2)}$ and end $t^{(4)}$ times of the symport (see Section IV-C). To validate the results, we compare the values obtained from (19) with the numerically simulated symport duration. The top panel of Fig. 8 shows the symport duration, $t^{(4)} - t^{(2)}$, and the bottom panel shows the final extravesicular S concentration $C_{\text{out}}^S(t^{(3)})$ for varying $\hat{\gamma}_L$ and $\hat{\gamma}_{\text{Sym}}^S$, which may correspond to different types of symporters and vesicle membranes, respectively. Note that a minimum illumination duration (denoted by the vertical black line in Fig. 8) is required to reach $C_{\xi}^{\text{H}^+}$ and to ensure that a cycle exhibits symporter activity. First, we observe that the symport duration increases approximately linearly during illumination after the

Fig. 9. Experimentally measured $d_{\text{in},m} + 2d_{\text{mem}}$ for PMOXA₁₅-PDMS₆₈-PMOXA₁₅ triblock co-polymerosomes synthesized in dichloroethan (blue bars) and a log-normal fit (red curve) with parameters $l_{\text{ves}} = 39.74$ nm, $\mu_{\text{ves}} = 4.16 \log(\text{nm})$, and $\sigma_{\text{ves}} = 0.62$.

minimum required illumination time. Moreover, we observe that the higher $\hat{\gamma}_{\text{Sym}}^S$, the lower is the symport duration for a given illumination duration as the symporter-caused H^+ outflux is larger. Similarly, a higher leakage rate $\hat{\gamma}_L$ (green curves in Fig. 8) shortens the symport duration as it also causes a larger H^+ outflux. For a given $\hat{\gamma}_{\text{Sym}}^S$, the total concentration of released S during the illumination phase, $C_{\text{out}}^S(t^{(3)})$, is therefore lower for larger $\hat{\gamma}_L$ (see bottom panel in Fig. 8). In practice, $\hat{\gamma}_L$ depends on the type of vesicle membrane (e.g., lipid or polymeric) and the choice of I and can vary substantially. Hence, its impact has to be considered carefully in experimental design. When both $\hat{\gamma}_L$ and $\hat{\gamma}_{\text{Sym}}^S$ are small, i.e., $\hat{\gamma}_L = 5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ and $\hat{\gamma}_{\text{Sym}}^S \leq 0.005 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (blue curve in top panel), the curves for the symport duration do not exhibit linear behavior. Instead, the symport duration first increases quickly but then more slowly as the illumination duration increases. Moreover, we observe a slight deviation between our analytical approximation for the symport duration (dashed lines in Fig. 8) and the duration obtained from FDM (solid lines in Fig. 8) for $\hat{\gamma}_L = 5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ and $\hat{\gamma}_{\text{Sym}}^S \leq 0.005 \text{ s}^{-1}$. This deviation is caused by a large $C_{\text{in,eq}}^{\text{H}^+}$ for a low H^+ outflux which causes the analytical approximation for the buffer effect to deviate more substantially from its actual values (as described in Section VI-A). Figure 8 also shows that the leakage flux has a substantial impact on the symport duration, $t^{(4)} - t^{(2)}$, i.e., the responsiveness of the ND to external stimuli, while the symport rate constant determines the strength of the chemical signal, i.e., $C_{\text{out}}^S(t)$. These observations can guide the choice of co-transporters for the release module and the choice of the vesicle membrane.

D. Multiple Vesicle System

Now, we consider an MVS consisting of n_{ves} NDs. Therefore, parameters d_{in} , $\hat{\gamma}_L$, n_p , and n_{Sym} are randomly distributed as described in Section V-A, where the parameter values of the distributions are given in the right-most columns of Table II. Figure 9 shows the experimentally measured distribution of the total vesicle diameter, i.e., $d_{\text{in},m} + 2d_{\text{mem}}$, and the corresponding fitted log-normal distribution. It is apparent that the log-normal distribution (see (22) in Section V-A) with parameters $l_{\text{ves}} = 39.74$ nm, $\mu_{\text{ves}} = 4.16 \log(\text{nm})$, and

Fig. 10. Histogram of the varied H^+ permeability values over the membrane using $l_L = -5.77$, $u_L = -5.27$, $\mu_L = -5.52$, $\sigma_L = 0.25$.

Fig. 11. Binomial distribution (red) and histogram of generated Binomially distributed random variables (blue bars) for the number of pumps, n_p , in the vesicle membrane of a vesicle with $d_{in} = 117.67$ nm, which corresponds to the mean of the log-normal distribution (in Fig. 9), and $n_{tot} = 112$ (for the given d_{in}).

$\sigma_{ves} = 0.62$ is an adequate fit for the experimental data.⁶ Interestingly, Fig. 9 shows that there is a physical minimum of the total vesicle diameter of approximately 40 nm for the given data set. This minimum is likely governed by the vesicle production process, membrane thickness, and the interactions between the membrane molecules. Such a clear physical limit does not seem to exist for the maximum vesicle diameter, as the experimental data shows a heavy tail towards large vesicle diameters, leading to a skewed distribution. This behavior is adequately captured by a shifted log-normal distribution, which has a lower but no upper bound. Figure 10 shows the histogram of values for $\hat{\gamma}_L$ sampled from a truncated log-normal distribution (see (24)). Similarly, Fig. 11 shows the Binomial distribution and sampled random variables for the number of pumps n_p for a vesicle with $d_{in} = 117.67$ nm (mean diameter from Fig. 9).

For the following results, we distinguish between the behavior of different SVSs, i.e., NDs, and the behavior of several MVS, i.e., experiments. Figure 12 shows the variation between

⁶Polymersomes were formed from the amphiphilic triblock copolymer poly(2)-methylloxazoline)₁₅-poly(dimethylsiloxane)₆₈-poly(2)-methylloxazoline)₁₅ (PMOXA₁₅-PDMS₆₈-PMOXA₁₅). The production process was carried out in the miniaturized stirred-tank reactor system bioREACTOR 48 (2mag, Munich, Germany) with a working volume of 12 ml [64]. A volume of 600 μ L of a 20% (weight/volume) ethanolic polymer solution was added to the buffer (20 mol m⁻³ potassium phosphate buffer, 150 mol m⁻³ potassium chloride, pH 8) in a 1:20 ratio (resulting in a 1% (weight/volume) polymer concentration) and then stirred at 4000 rpm and 30 °C with an S-shaped stirrer. The vesicle size distribution was determined by dynamic light scattering (ZetaSizer Nano series, Malvern Panalytcs GmbH, Kassel, Germany). The fabrication process was terminated after one hour, when a polydispersity index of less than 0.2 was achieved.

different NDs within one experiment (top panels) and between the MVSs of different experiments (bottom panels). The inter-vesicle and inter-experiment means are shown as solid and dashed lines in the top and bottom panels of Fig. 12, respectively. Similarly, the shaded area around the means shows one standard deviation for the inter-vesicle and -experiment results. The number of experiments was $n_{exp} = 10$ while the number of individually modeled vesicles per experiment was $n_{mod} = 100$. This means that, while we assume that our MVS consists of $n_{ves} = 10^{11}$ vesicles and divide $\mathcal{V}_{out,tot}$ accordingly, we only model a small fraction of these vesicles ($n_{mod} \ll n_{ves}$) to limit computational complexity. The results from FDM (blue curves) in Fig. 12 were calculated using the total extravascular H^+ concentration, $C_{out,tot}^{H^+}(t)$, and serve as a baseline. According to (A4), the analytical approximation assumes total independence of all subsystems and therefore refrains from computing $C_{out,tot}^{H^+}(t)$. Additionally, Fig. 12 shows the expected behavior of an SVS based on the mean parameter values for $n_p, n_{Sym}, \hat{\gamma}_L$, and d_{in} of the MVS (black dashed line). From the top panels of Fig. 12, it can be observed that the inter-vesicle variance is substantial, as reflected by the large standard deviation of $C_{in}^{H^+}(t)$ and $C_{out}^S(t)$. This means that the behavior of individual NDs within one MVS is diverse and inhomogeneous. Additionally, the mean responses of $C_{in}^{H^+}(t)$ and $C_{out}^S(t)$ are not equal to the response of a vesicle with average parameters. This observation suggests that careful consideration of the parameter distribution is required to adequately model the behavior of the vesicles that occur in chemical realizations. Similarly, the mean behavior of the MVSs (bottom panel of Fig. 12) also deviates from the corresponding mean SVS, as expected from Theorem 1. In fact, as the influence of the random parameter $d_{in,m}$ results in squared and cubic changes in the intravesicular volume and the transport rates, the mean $C_{out}^S(t)$ of an SVS clearly lies below the inter-experiment mean of the MVSs (bottom right panel in Fig. 12). Notably, the inter-experiment variance is much less substantial than the inter-vesicle variance. As stated in Theorem 2, the inter-experiment variance tends to 0 as the number of vesicles per experiment tends to infinity. As the number of vesicles in experiments is expected to be around 10^{11} ml⁻¹, the inter-experiment variance is likely negligible in realistic setups. We point out that, in Fig. 12, the differences between the FDM baseline and our analytical approximation are similarly small as for the SVS, where they result from the constant buffer attenuation factor. Consequently, for the MVS, the deviations from the baseline in Fig. 12 are also expected to (mostly) originate from the constant buffer attenuation rather than the violation of (A4). This is in line with our expectation that considering SVS independence for the analytical approximation does not cause a substantial error when $V_{out,m} \gg V_{in,m}$, as would be the case for most experimental settings. If $V_{out,m} \gg V_{in,m}$, the fluxes from and to $\mathcal{V}_{out,m}$ lead to small concentration changes in $V_{out,m}$ due to its large volume size. Generally, the analysis of MVSs clearly indicates that considering multiple NDs within realistic TXs is crucial as their behavior deviates from the expected behavior of a single ND. Nevertheless, the behavior of the

Fig. 12. Top: Inter-vesicle intravesicular H^+ and extravascular S concentration mean (solid or dashed line) \pm one standard deviation (shaded area). Bottom: Inter-experiment H^+ and extravascular S concentration mean (solid line) \pm one standard deviation (shaded area). Here, $n_{\text{mod}} = 100$ vesicles per simulation were modeled individually and $n_{\text{exp}} = 10$ simulations were averaged for the bottom row. The shaded area corresponds to the illumination time.

Fig. 13. Mean and one standard deviation of the intravesicular H^+ (left) and extravascular S concentrations (right) for varying mean inner vesicle diameters. The chosen mean vesicle diameters were $\bar{d}_{\text{in}} \in \{100, 500, 1000\}$ nm. The shaded area corresponds to the illumination time.

overall MVS is consistent among different experiments. This indicates that future wet lab implementations of the system will be reproducible and, thus, reliable.

E. Varying Mean Values for Parameters in Different Experimental Batches

In practice, when multiple experiments are conducted using different batches of proteins, buffers, and polymers, the distributions of the parameters may vary between experiments. To account for such effects, we conduct a sensitivity analysis to investigate the influence of practically relevant parameters, which should be carefully tuned in order to reduce inter-experiment variance. Such analyses are beneficial for future experimental realizations of the system where the variance

between batches has to be taken into account. For the analysis, we focus on the mean inner vesicle diameter \bar{d}_{in} and the mean leakage velocity over the membrane $\bar{\gamma}_L$. These values may vary depending on the production process, which cannot be controlled perfectly. For the following results, $n_{\text{exp}} = 10$ experiments were conducted per setting, each consisting of $n_{\text{ves}} = 100$ individually modeled vesicles.

1) *Varying Mean Inner Vesicle Diameters:* Figure 13 shows the impact of different mean vesicle diameters \bar{d}_{in} on the inter-experiment variance for $n_{\text{exp}} = 10$ experiments, while the variance of its distribution remains unchanged. As \bar{d}_{in} directly influences V_{in} , it also scales $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)$ (see left panel in Fig. 13). For example, larger vesicles exhibit a lower intravesicular concentration change upon illumination. Therefore, we also

Fig. 14. Mean and one standard deviation of the intravesicular H^+ (left) and extravesicular S concentrations (right) for varying mean H^+ permeability coefficient, $\tilde{\gamma}_L$. The chosen permeability coefficients were $\tilde{\gamma}_L \in \{1, 5, 10\} \times 10^{-6} \text{ m s}^{-1}$. The shaded area corresponds to the illumination time.

observe a delayed start of symport for these vesicles (see right panel in Fig. 13). Similarly, as n_{Sym} increases with d_{in} and directly scales the symport rate, larger vesicles have a higher symport rate, which is reflected in a higher incline of $C_{\text{out}}^S(t)$ during symport. Therefore, a quicker S release during symport by large vesicles comes at the trade-off of lower system responsiveness. The leakage and symport rate are proportional to the outer vesicle area, which is linearly dependent on d_{in}^2 . However, as V_{in} grows linearly in d_{in}^3 , the effect of increasing V_{in} dominates the effect of increasing leakage and symport rate, as can be observed from the curves for $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)$ in Fig. 13. We observe that the absolute inter-experiment variance of $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)$ is largest for small mean vesicle diameters in Fig. 13. The cause of this is also the cubic dependence of V_{in} on d_{in} . In conclusion, Fig. 13 indicates that changes in \bar{d}_{in} greatly impact the release of S. Thus, parameter \bar{d}_{in} should be tuned carefully to obtain the desired system behavior.

2) *Varying Mean Permeability Coefficient:* Figure 14 shows a similar analysis for different mean H^+ permeability coefficients $\tilde{\gamma}_L$ of the membrane. Similar to Fig. 13, the results were obtained using MVS and averaging over $n_{\text{exp}} = 10$ simulations. For this analysis, the values of $\tilde{\gamma}_L$ were varied between 10^{-6} m s^{-1} and 10^{-5} m s^{-1} . The left panel shows that there is a correlation between low permeability coefficients and high $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)$ during illumination. Naturally, this also implies that our analytical solution performs worse for lower permeabilities as the buffering effect is modeled inadequately (refer to Section VI-A). Interestingly, for the chosen threshold ξ , $C_{\text{out}}^S(t)$ does not depend as strongly on $\tilde{\gamma}_L$ (see right panel in Fig. 14). However, the differences between the symport end times $t_1^{(4)}$ after $t_1^{(3)} = 800 \text{ s}$ can be seen clearly: For $\tilde{\gamma}_L = 10^{-5} \text{ m s}^{-1}$, $C_{\text{out}}^S(t)$ quickly stagnates, indicating that the symport ends shortly after the end of illumination. This is directly related to the lower $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)$ for the respective permeability coefficient. A lower permeability coefficient and, thus, higher $C_{\text{in}}^{\text{H}^+}(t)$ causes the symporters to remain active after illumination ends, which is why we cannot observe any stagnation in $C_{\text{out}}^S(t)$ for $\tilde{\gamma}_L = 10^{-6} \text{ m s}^{-1}$. We observe that the changes in $C_{\text{out}}^S(t)$ are less substantial when varying $\tilde{\gamma}_L$ than when varying \bar{d}_{in} . Note that the y-axes in Figs. 13 and 14 differ by a magnitude of 100. This is because, unlike \bar{d}_{in} , $\tilde{\gamma}_L$ scales only some transport rate (it does not scale the S transport rate of the release

modules, for instance). Therefore, if the envisioned application is sensitive to the amount of released S, it is important to keep \bar{d}_{in} constant among experimental realizations, while small deviations in $\tilde{\gamma}_L$ are likely less impactful.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we introduced a new ND design that can be used as an optically controllable TX in synthetic MC systems and facilitates the release of SMs from a vesicle by leveraging cooperating transmembrane transport proteins. The proposed modular design comprises an energizing module and a release module powered by the energizing module and has the potential to be useful in various future healthcare and industrial applications of MC as it supports the controlled release of a variety of different SMs. The proposed TX design is not only versatile but also more realistic than many of the TX models considered in the MC literature, as it can be chemically implemented. The proposed model includes practically relevant effects, such as non-instantaneous SM release and SM depletion, that are disregarded in existing TX models. Not considering such effects during system modeling may be detrimental to the performance of future MC systems, as preliminarily analyzed in [28]. We proposed two analytical expressions for the concentrations of the involved molecules to describe the dynamics of the envisioned ND and successfully verified them by comparison to a numerical baseline for both unbuffered and buffered scenarios. Our results demonstrate that the choice of appropriate system parameters, such as the ratio of pumps and co-transporters or the buffer molarity, is crucial for ensuring the feasibility of the desired system behavior. Consequently, the proposed analytical solutions can guide the design of future experiments and thereby accelerate the development time of the envisioned ND by offering the possibility for *in silico* optimization of the system parameters. Additionally, this work is a crucial step towards modeling experimentally feasible MC TXs by accounting for the fact that practically implementable TX systems consist of large groups of NDs. Moreover, we considered realistic random distributions for various system parameters caused by the chemical production of vesicular NDs and modeled ND diversity. An interesting topic for future work is a more detailed investigation of the behavior of the components of the

system, e.g., by modeling the dependency that the applied light intensity has on the molecule transport rates and by developing more sophisticated models for the symport kinetics.

APPENDIX

A. Proof of Theorem 1

In order to prove Theorem 1, we need to show that one of the functions describing the S and I concentrations are not equal for the mean of the MVS with varying parameters d_{in} , n_P , n_{Sym} , and $\hat{\gamma}_L$ and the corresponding SVS with the mean parameters \bar{d}_{in} , \bar{n}_P , \bar{n}_{Sym} , and $\bar{\gamma}_L$. To this end, we use Jensen's inequality for convex function, $\phi : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ [65, Sec. 2.7]:

$$\phi(\mathcal{E}\{X\}) \leq \mathcal{E}\{\phi(X)\}, \quad (26)$$

where X and $\mathcal{E}\{\cdot\}$ are a random variable and the expectation operation, respectively. The inequality in (26) becomes an equality iff X is constant, i.e., deterministic, or iff the function ϕ is affine, i.e., linear [66, Sec. 8.4]. Let us consider (12) and random variable $X := n_{Sym}$. If we rewrite $C_{in}^S(t)$ for the case of symporter activity in terms of X and some constants β_i with $i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$, we obtain:

$$C_{in}^S(t, X) = \beta_1 W \left\{ \beta_2 \exp\{\beta_3 - \beta_4 X(t - \tau(t))\} \right\}. \quad (27)$$

Now, let us take the second derivative of $C_{in}^S(t, X)$ with respect to the random variable X . We consequently obtain:

$$C_{in}^{S''}(t, X) = \beta_1 (\beta_4(t - \tau(t)))^2 \times \frac{W \left\{ \beta_2 \exp\{\beta_3 - \beta_4 X(t - \tau(t))\} \right\}}{(1 + W \left\{ \beta_2 \exp\{\beta_3 - \beta_4 X(t - \tau(t))\} \right\})^3}. \quad (28)$$

This equation holds for all $t \geq \tau(t)$. All β_i are strictly positive. Additionally, the Lambert W-function yields positive values for positive arguments. Consequently, we observe that $C_{in}^{S''}(t, X) \geq 0$, i.e., $C_{in}^S(t, X)$ is convex. Therefore, we can use Jensen's inequality to relate the function value at the expectation of X to the expectation of the function evaluated at X . As X is a (positive) non-deterministic random variable, we conclude that the following holds:

$$\mathcal{E}\{C_{in}^S(X)\} \neq C_{in}^S(\mathcal{E}\{X\}). \quad (29)$$

This suffices to conclude that $C_{in}^S(t)$ in an SVS with average parameters does not correspond to the signal in the overall MVS. Therefore, we have shown that the MVS behavior cannot be captured by the models derived for the SVS with average parameters if the symporters are activated at some point. Note that similar results can be obtained when considering the other random parameters, but the derivations are omitted here. \square

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